

The Development of Character Education Model using Stop Motion Animation for Elementary School Students in Indonesia

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to develop character education model using Stop Motion Animation for elementary school students in Jakarta in Indonesia. This Research and Development (R&D) built four Stop Motion Animations related to character education in teaching learning process, school culture, extracurricular activities, and through community involvement. These products were developed using animation technique involving manipulating physical objects in creating the illusion of motion with Stop Motion Animation software. Validation of experts attained 3.63 from scores ranging 1 to 4 pointing out that this model is already valid in character education. Validation of restricted and extensive field test reached 3.86 and 3.80 from scores ranging 1 to 4. These products had been revised based on recommendation from expert and field test connected with the content and presentation technique. It can be stated that this model is highly practical and effective to implement character education for elementary school students in Jakarta in Indonesia.

Keywords: character education; stop motion animation; school culture; extracurricular activities; community involvement

1. Introduction

As stated in Indonesia Republic Constitution number 30, system of national education in Indonesia has the intention of achieving to create Indonesian student positive characters leading to have national way of living. The regulation of Indonesia Republic President number 87 presents that educational institution in Indonesia has to ensure in strengthening student character building. However, elementary schools as educational institutions in Indonesia generally make the cognitive aspect of education a focus of attention, consequently, the student character building encouragement managed has not been most favourable.

Student character is related to moral action associated with belief and fundamental attitudes of individual (Sarros & Cooper, 2006). The building of student character can be directed through activities in teaching learning process (Marini, 2019). Study conducted by Milson & Mehlig (2002) found that the teacher at elementary schools has more efficacy on character education. Student positive characters can be encouraged by implementation of character building in teaching learning process (Marini, 2019; Izfanna and Hisyam, 2012). Character building program can enhance the student positive behavior (Thompson, 2002). Development of student positive characters can be implemented in teaching learning process, school culture, extracurricular activities, and community involvement (Marini, 2019; Oktarina, Widiyanto, and Soekardi, 2015). Character education applied in religious school culture can develop student religious character (Marini, 2018). However, the

previous studies are not associated with computer assisted character building, specifically for simulation games.

2. Literature review

Sarros & Cooper (2006) stated that character building has to be conducted through three phases consisting of it is knowing morally involving moral awareness and reason to take a appropriate action, having moral feeling related to do the right things, and having moral action related to the action together with competences and willingness. Integration of character value in preparation of teaching learning process is predicted by praying, associating teaching material given with improvement of student positive attitude, and examining the neatness of student uniform (Marini, 2019). Character building in the core of teaching learning process in influenced by guiding the students to cooperate one another in group task, motivating the students to ask questions bravely, and taking priority of building student attitude. In closing activities of teaching learning process, student character building is estimated by praying together, greeting between teacher and students. Study conducted by Milson & Mehlig (2002) found the method to develop elementary school teachers' competencies for character building at schools. Integration of character values in preparation, core, and closing of teaching learning process predicted character building in teaching learning process (Marini, 2019; Izfanna and Hisyam, 2012). It is stated that the student prudence encourages the student character. Character education should be an integral part of the curriculum at elementary schools (Thompson, 2002). The teachers has to be a good character model for the students. The students should get involved in hands-on service activities of the character building program in contributing to the school and society in general. Integration of character values implemented in teaching learning process through preparation, core, and closing activities encourage the building of student character in class (Marini, 2019). This study found that the student prudence influenced the student character. The process of integrating character values at school was implemented in teaching learning process, school culture, extracurricular activities, and community involvement (Marini, 2019; Oktarina, Widiyanto, and Soekardi, 2015). The enhancement of student positive characters done through religious school culture by school providing worship facilities, religious ceremonies and religious symbols motivated the religious character of the students promoted by obedience in carrying out the teachings of one's religions, the practice of religious tolerance towards others and living in harmony with other religions (Marini, 2018). However, the previous studies done were not related to computer assisted character building, especially for applying stop motion animation.

3. Method

The aim of this study is to develop character education model using Stop Motion Animation for elementary school students in Jakarta in Indonesia. This Research and Development consists of needs analysis to collect some information, designs and development, and expert validation of character education model using Stop Motion Animation for elementary school students in Jakarta in Indonesia. Data collection was conducted by applying evaluation instrument for character education model using Stop Motion Animation for elementary school students in Jakarta in Indonesia. The technique of descriptive quantitative was used in data analysis.

4. Results and Discussion

On the basis of observation conducted at 145 public elementary schools in Jakarta in Indonesia stated that the school management on the basis of character building implemented in teaching learning process, school culture, extracurricular activities, and through community involvement with higher scores than the average of effectiveness attained 56.6 %, 56.50 %, 73.80 %, and 24.80 %,

respectively, and with lower scores than the average of effectiveness reached 25.5 %, 37.40 %, 6.20 %, and 64.90 %, respectively (seen in Figure 1, 2, 3, and 4).

Figure 1. Scores of school management based on character building in teaching learning process

Figure 2. Scores of school management based on character building in school culture

Figure 3. Scores of school management based on character building in extracurricular activities

Figure 4. Scores of school management based on character building through community involvement

On the basis of this survey result, this research designed and developed character education model using Stop Motion Animation for elementary school students in Jakarta in Indonesia in order to improve the effectiveness of character education implementation. Theoretical model of character education using Stop Motion Animation for elementary school students in Jakarta in Indonesia can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Theoretical model of character education using Stop Motion Animation for elementary school students

It can be seen in Figure 1 that model of character education using Stop Motion Animation for elementary school students consists of character building in teaching learning process, school culture, extracurricular activities, and through community involvement leading to have effective school management based on character building. Character building in teaching learning process is related to the teacher maintaining student activity and creativity in teaching learning process and the teacher conducting two-way communication with the students. Character building in school culture is associated with nationalism school culture through the teacher motivating the students to participate in following the ceremony of national big day. Character building in extracurricular activities is related to the teacher motivating the students to actively participate in extracurricular activities and the teacher integrating character values in extracurricular activities. Character building through community involvement is associated with the community involvement to take care of securing the school and solve the problems associated with character education at school.

In this research, the model using Stop Motion Animation was combined with 2-dimension animation-based character education for elementary school students in Jakarta in Indonesia for building student characters integrated in learning with 2-dimension animation. This product was created to attract student attention and stimulate student interest related to the improvement of student character building. Creation of 2D animation videos in this research used Adobe Illustrator, Adobe After Effect, and Adobe Premiere softwares. Adobe Illustrator is a software related to create a graphic design in making this animated video for making characters. Adobe After Effect is a software related to create animations. Making this animated video was conducted to make animated writing and characters. Adobe Premiere is a software related to edit videos. Making this animated video was done to mix between animations made and audio needed. Figure 1, 2, 3, and 4 shows animated film with theme 1 about character building in teaching learning process, theme 2 about character building in school culture, theme 3 about character building in extracurricular activities, and theme 4 about character building through community involvement.

Figure 1. Animated film with theme 1 about character building in teaching learning process

Figure 2. Character building in school culture

Figure 3. Character building in extracurricular activities

Figure 4. Animated film with theme 4 about character building through community involvement

Expert validation of character education model using Stop Motion Animation for elementary school students in Jakarta in Indonesia achieved 3.63 from scores ranging 1 to 4 indicating that this model is already valid. Validation of restricted and extensive field test arrived at 3.86 and 3.80 from maximum score 4. These products had been revised based on suggestion from expert and field test related to the content and presentation technique.

Conclusion

It can be concluded that character education model using Stop Motion Animation for elementary school students in Jakarta in Indonesia is already valid as well as highly practical and effective to be applied for elementary school students in Jakarta in Indonesia. It is expected that this product can be implemented as a model of character education to stimulate the student interest to be engaged with character education conducted leading to improvement of student positive characters.

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